

The synthetic *trans*-7-dodecenyl acetate showed IR maxima at 1730 and 1040 cm^{-1} characteristic of a primary acetate group. It also showed a sharp band at 980 cm^{-1} characteristic of the C-H out of plane deformation of the *trans* disubstituted double bond. The peak at 970 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectrum of the *cis*-7-dodecenyl acetate was absent.

*The mass spectral data for 7-dodecenyl acetate showed a strong parent peak at 226 m/e. The (p+1) peak was observed distinctly. The characteristic fragmentation peaks shown by acetyl esters was observed at 43 and 60 m/e. A strong peak at 70 m/e was observed, accounting for the ion formed by the breaking of the ethylenic linkage at carbon seven. The mass spectrum data is consistent with the proposed structure of 7-dodecenyl acetate.

In preliminary screening tests, the cabbage looper and the false codling moth hormones synthesized were used as bait in field trapping experiments. *Cis*-7-dodecenyl acetate caught two male cabbage looper moths over a 14-day period. Naturally-occurring lures were not used as a standard for comparison. Extensive work remains to be done in the area of screening techniques to standardize a systematic procedure to screen samples for activity. At the present time the data obtained from the preliminary screenings are inconclusive and do not provide definite results regarding the physiological activity of the hormones synthesized.

Experimental

Spectra were obtained using a Varian A-60D analytical NMR spectrometer. The samples were run both as neat liquid and in deuterated organic solvents, at ambient magnetic temperature, 39°. A filter band width of 4 Hz, a RF field of 0.015 to 0.1 mG, a sweep time of 250 sec., and a sweep width of 500 Hz were used. All spectral data obtained are reported in (δ) values with respect to tetramethyl silane peak. The IR spectra were obtained as thin films between sodium chloride plates in the region of 4000 cm^{-1} to 600 cm^{-1} using a Perkin-Elmer Model 700 spectrophotometer. Molecular weights were determined using a DuPont Model 21-490, 90° single focusing mass spectrometer. Cyclohexene, obtained from Eastman Kodak Chemical Company, was used without further purification. Periodic acid, obtained from Matheson Chemical Company, Inc., was used without further purification. Peroxyacetic acid, 40%, in acetic acid was prepared using the procedure reported in the literature¹⁰. All other chemicals and solvents used were reagent grade.

1, 2-epoxycyclohexane(II): Peroxyacetic acid, 40%, (70 g, 0.5 m) dissolved in acetic acid (80 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred, cooled (20°) solution of anhydrous sodium acetate (41.0 g, 0.5 m) and cyclohexene (41 g, 0.50 m) in chloroform (700 ml). The mixture was stirred at 50° for 2 hrs. and allowed to stir an additional 8 hrs. at room

temperature. The solution was neutralized with a 1.0 N solution of sodium bicarbonate. The organic layer was separated, washed with water (200 ml), and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed in vacuo and the residue was distilled to afford 43.6 g (89% yield) of (II). bp: 49° (8 mm) [Lit¹¹ bp: 54° (10 mm)]; ¹H NMR (CDCl_3), 1.4 (t, 4H), 2.0 (m, 4H), 3.2 (t, 2H), (Found C. 73.51; H. 10.29; calc. for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}$, C. 73.46; H. 10.20).

1, 6-hexanedial(III): Periodic acid (91.2 g, 0.4 m) was added in five gram portions to a stirred suspension of 1, 2-epoxycyclohexane (39.2 g, 0.4 m) in water (500 ml). As the reaction proceeded the contents were cooled with an ice bath to prevent the temperature from rising above 45°. The addition of periodic acid was completed in 3 hrs. The mixture was allowed to stir at 25° for an additional 5 hrs. The solution was neutralized with solid sodium bicarbonate to pH 7. The neutral solution was saturated with sodium chloride and allowed to stand at room temperature for 4 hrs. The solution was subsequently extracted with chloroform (8 × 100 ml). The combined organic fractions were washed with water (500 ml) and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed under vacuum to afford 41.5 g of (III), as a yellow liquid. ¹H NMR (neat), 1.8 (t, 4H), 2.6 (m, 4H), 9.8 (d, 2H).

6-ethylenedioxy-1-hexanal(IV): A solution of 1,6-hexanedial, (35.0 g, 0.3 m), ethylene glycol (18.6 g, 0.3 m), *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (100 mg), and anhydrous benzene (500 ml) was refluxed for 12 hrs. The water formed during the reaction was removed using a Dean-Stark apparatus. The solution was cooled to room temperature, filtered, washed with 0.10 N sodium bicarbonate, and dried (MgSO_4). Benzene was removed using a rotary evaporator and the residue upon distillation gave 45 g (95% yield) of (IV). bp: 118° (20 mm); ¹H NMR (neat), 1.6 (m, 8H), 4.0 (s, 4H), 4.9 (m, 1H), 9.8 (d, 1H).

1-pentyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (V): A stirring mixture of *n*-bromopentane (75.5 g, 0.5 m), triphenylphosphine (131 g, 0.5 m), and toluene (200 ml) was refluxed for 8 hrs. The solution was cooled to room temperature and anhydrous ether (200 ml) was added to separate the phosphonium salt. The salt was isolated by filtration, washed with anhydrous ether and recrystallized from methanol to give 123 g (60% yield) of (V) as a white crystalline solid. Mp: 163-165°; [Lit¹² mp 167°]; ¹H NMR (CDCl_3), 0.9 (t, 3H), 1.6 (m, 6H), 3.8 (m, 2H), 7.9 (m, 15H).

11-ethylenedioxy-5-undecene (VI): A solution of 1-pentyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (82.6 g, 0.2 ml), sodium ethoxide (13.6 g, 0.2 ml), and ethanol (300 ml) was treated dropwise with a solution of 6-ethylenedioxy-1-hexanal (31.6 g, 0.2 ml) in ethanol (100 ml). After the addition was completed, the reaction mixture was allowed to stir for

2 hrs. at 40°. The solution was cooled and allowed to stand at room temperature for 24 hrs. The solution was filtered and extracted with ether (5×200 ml). The combined ether extracts were washed with water (5×100 ml) and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvent in vacuum gave 27 g of (VI) as a yellow liquid. ¹H NMR (neat), 0.8 (t, 3H), 1.5 (m, 14H), 3.8 (s, 4H), 4.8 (m, 1H), 5.8 (t, 2H).

6-undecene-1-al (VII) : A solution of 11-ethylenedioxy-5-undecene (25 g, 0.11 ml) and hydrochloric acid 0.10 N (100 ml) was refluxed at 95° for 4 hrs. The hot solution was poured into water (200 ml) and neutralized with 0.50 N sodium hydroxide. The aqueous solution was saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with chloroform (5×100 ml). The combined chloroform extracts were washed with water (2×100 ml) and dried (Na₂SO₄). The chloroform was removed under vacuum and the residue upon distillation gave 16.6 g (90% yield) of (VII). bp : 126° (10 mm); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), 1.0 (t, 3H), 1.6 (m, 12H), 2.4 (m, 2H), 5.8 (t, 2H), 9.6 (d, 2H). (Found C. 78.73; H. 12.01; calc. for C₁₁H₂₀O, C. 78.57, H. 11.90).

6-undecene-1-ol (VIII) : A mixture of 6-undecene-1-ol (15.2 g, 0.9 ml), sodium borohydride (4.5 g, 0.1 ml), and ethanol (200 ml) was stirred for 4 hrs. at 40°. The reaction mixture was allowed to stir for an additional 2 hrs. at room temperature and then poured into a beaker of distilled water (500 ml). The solution was saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with chloroform (3×100 ml). The combined chloroform extracts were washed with water (300 ml) and dried (MgSO₄). The chloroform was removed in vacuum and the residue was distilled to afford 14.9 g (97% yield) of (VIII). bp : 114-116° (12 mm); ¹H NMR (neat), 0.9 (t, 3H), 1.6 (m, 14H), 3.8 (m, 2H), 4.8 (s, 1H), 5.7 (t, 2H). (Found C. 77.81; H. 13.02; calc. for C₁₁H₂₂O, C. 77.64; H. 12.94).

1-bromo-6-undecene (IX) : A solution of phosphorus tribromide (13.5 g, 0.050 m), lithium bromide (4.4 g, 0.050 m), in pyridine (25 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred, cooled solution of 6-undecene-1-ol (9 g, 0.050 m) in pyridine (25 ml). Throughout the addition the temperature was maintained at -30° using a slurry of acetone and liquid nitrogen. Following the addition the reaction mixture was refluxed at 80° for 2 hrs. The solution was cooled to room temperature and poured into a beaker of crushed ice. The solution was extracted with ether (3×100 ml). The combined ether extracts were washed with 1.0 N hydrochloric acid (5×250 ml) to separate pyridine as its hydrochloride salt. The ether layer then was washed with 1.0 N solution bicarbonate (2×200 ml), water (2×100 ml), and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the ether under vacuum gave 111 g of (IX) in the form of a brown liquid. ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), 0.9 (t, 3H), 1.2-1.6 (m, 14H), 3.5 (m, 2H), 5.6 (t, 2H).

1-cyano-6-undecene (X) : A solution of sodium cyanide (4.9 g, 0.10 m), copper cyanide (8.9 g, 0.10 m), and a 1-bromo-6-undecene (10 g, 0.040 m) in dimethylformamide (50 ml) was refluxed at 90° for 16 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and poured into a cold saturated solution of sodium chloride (200 ml). The solution was filtered and the aqueous solution was extracted with benzene (3×100 ml). The combined organic extracts were washed with water (2×100 ml) and dried (MgSO₄). The benzene was evaporated under vacuum to yield 9 g of (X). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), 0.9 (t, 3H), 1.6 (m, 14H), 4.0 (m, 2H), 5.6 (t, 2H).

1-amino-7-dodecene (XI) : Sodium borohydride (11.4 g, 0.30 m) was added in small portions to a stirred solution of 1-cyano-6-undecene (6.5 g, 0.036 m) and cobalt chloride hexahydrate (11.4 g, 0.3 m) in ethanol (200 ml). The temperature throughout the addition was maintained at 25° using a water bath. A black precipitate appeared during the addition of sodium borohydride. When the addition was complete, stirring was continued for 2 hrs. at 25°. Hydrochloric acid 2.0 N (100 ml) was poured into the reaction mixture and stirred until the black precipitate dissolved. Ethanol was removed from the solution by distillation. Any unreacted nitrile was removed from the residue by extraction with ether (2×100 ml). The aqueous layer was made alkaline with ammonium hydroxide. The alkaline solution was extracted with ether (3×100 ml). The combined ether extracts were washed with saturated sodium chloride solution (2×100 ml), water (1×100 ml), and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was removed under vacuo and the residue upon distillation gave 6.0 g (92% yield) of (XI). bp : 96° (5 mm); ¹H NMR (neat), 1.0 (t, 3H), 1.7 (m, 12H), 3.4 (m, 6H), 5.6 (t, 2H). (Found C. 78.82; H. 13.61; N. 7.83; calc. for C₁₂H₂₅N, C. 78.68; H. 13.66; N. 7.65).

7-dodecenol (XII) : Concentrated sulfuric acid (20 ml) was added dropwise to a suspension of 1-amino-7-dodecene (6.0 g, 0.030 m) in water (100 ml). The clear solution was cooled to -3° using an ice bath. A solution of sodium nitrite (17 g, 0.25 m) in water (30 ml) was added dropwise to the cold amine solution. Following the addition of sodium nitrite the solution was allowed to stir at 0°. After 2 hrs., ice (100 g) and urea (1 g) were added to the cold solution. The solution was evaporated to 100 ml by gradual heating. The aqueous solution was cooled to room temperature and extracted with ether (2×100 ml). The residue was neutralized with 3.0 N sodium hydroxide. The neutral solution was extracted with ether (3×100 ml). The combined ether extracts were washed with water (2×200 ml) and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvent gave 5.1 g of (XII) as a pale yellow liquid. ¹H NMR (neat), 1.0 (t, 3H), 1.6 (m, 16H), 3.8 (t, 2H), 4.2 (s, 1H), 5.8 (t, 2H).

7-dodecanyl acetate (XIII) : A mixture of 7-dodecenol (8.0 g, 0.05 m) and acetyl chloride (15.5 g,

0.2 m) was stirred at 45° for 11 hr. The solution was cooled to room temperature and poured into a beaker (500 ml) of crushed ice. A yellow organic layer separated to the top. The organic layer was washed with 0.10 N sodium bicarbonate solution (100 ml), water (2×100 ml), and dried (CaCl₂). The organic layer was distilled under reduced pressure to yield 5.5 g (90% yield) of (XIII) as a colorless liquid. bp: 78-85° (0.05 mm) [Lit⁶ bp: 78-82 (0.05 mm)]; ¹H NMR (neat), 0.8 (t, 3H), 1.4 (m, 16H), 1.8 (s, 3H), 4.2 (t, 2H), 5.8 (t, 2H). (Mol. wt. found 226; calc. for C₁₄H₂₆O₂, 226). (Found C. 74.42; H. 11.61; calc. for C₁₄H₂₆O₂, C. 74.33; H. 11.50).

Separation of cis and trans isomers of 7-dodecenyyl acetate: The *cis* and *trans* isomers were separated chromatographically using a column packed with silica gel impregnated with silver nitrate. The packing material for the column was prepared by drying a mixture of 20 g of silica gel and 60 ml of 15% aqueous silver nitrate in a rotary evaporator and then heating the mixture in an oven at 110° for 2 hrs. The *i*-dodecenyyl acetate (500 mg) was introduced on the silica gel-silver nitrate column and eluted with ether (3%) in hexane. The first fractions contained the *trans*-7-dodecenyyl acetate. The latter fraction eluted with ether (10%) in hexane contained the *cis*-7-dodecenyyl acetate. The *trans* isomer obtained was 340 mg (68%) and the *cis* isomer obtained was 90 mg (18%).

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